

IMPORTANCE OF INITIATIVES TO INCREASE NATIONAL COMPETITIVENESS IN TERMS OF ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT

Ali KONAK

Assoc. Prof. - Karabuk University, Faculty of Economics and Administrative Sciences,
Department of Economics,
Orcid: 0000-0003-1804-8339

Toshkent Amaliy Fanlar Universiteti, Iqtisodiyot Bo'limi

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Abstract. *One of the most important elements of economic development is the element of competition. A country's gaining national competitive power in economic terms is extremely important in terms of ensuring sustainable economic growth. National competition also contributes to the strengthening of national companies, allowing these companies to be commercially competitive in international markets and increasing the country's export revenues. In its most general form, economic development means the growth of a country by developing economically and the increase in the welfare levels of individuals who make up the society. In this context, it is possible to say that increases in national competitive power are of critical importance in terms of the country's economic development. Because in a country with high competitive power, both increases in production volume occur and product quality increases, and accordingly economic development occurs, and with this potential obtained, the country's competitive power in international markets increases. It is also possible to say that the development process in a country has the possibility of attracting more investment from abroad by enabling the development of the country's infrastructure. This prepared study will focus on the importance of increases in national competitive power in terms of economic development.*

Keywords: *Economic Development, National Competitiveness, Technology, Human Capital.*

1. INTRODUCTION

In its most general form, it is possible to define the concept of competition in economic terms as the competitive environment that companies or sectors face during the production process. In this competitive environment, companies strive to increase their profits and grow by producing the same or similar products at lower costs and in a more qualified manner compared to other companies. Carrying this competition to the international level contributes to a significant increase in the country's export revenues. It is possible to say that if the increases in export revenues are directed to investments, it will contribute to both national employment increases and improvements in welfare levels, as well as economic growth and development. Today, developments in many areas, especially in technology, have caused production activities to accelerate and product quality to increase. This process also causes intense competition between companies at both national and international levels. For this reason, companies, especially those engaged in foreign trade activities, must focus on what they need to do in order to sustain their existence, continue their commercial activities and increase their production volumes in the competitive environment they will face in both national and international markets. In addition, national governments have important duties in this process to ensure

economic growth and development. Because national governments can make significant contributions to the strengthening of national companies both at national and international levels with the economic incentives they will provide and the legal regulations that will facilitate commercial activities. To this end, governments can both implement direct fiscal policies and implement incentives and measures to implement monetary policies in this direction.

It is possible to say that it is extremely important to follow technological developments in order to increase national competitiveness, which is extremely important in economic terms, and to achieve economic development. Because technology is one of the most important parts of the production process. It is observed that businesses and sectors that invest in the technological field and use technology effectively in the production process show rapid development, there are increases in production volume and product quality also increases. Due to these benefits it provides in economic terms, investments to be made in the field of technology and innovation have gained great importance in recent years. Realizing the power and importance of new technologies in increasing national competitiveness, governments contribute to the technological development of the country by providing various state incentives for R&D activities. In addition, the private sector is encouraged to invest in technology through various channels by governments and an effort is being made to develop a university-industry cooperation mechanism. In addition, making the national investments necessary for the development and strengthening of the digital infrastructure that will enable the national economy to become competitive at a global level is also of great importance in this process. In addition, there is a great need for an educated and qualified workforce that will use advanced technologies in this process. Therefore, investments in education should be increased in order to have an educated workforce that will both increase the quality of education and use advanced technologies. In addition, it is extremely important for the state to provide incentives to encourage entrepreneurship and to reduce both bureaucratic and legal barriers in order to increase competitiveness at the national level. In this way, working conditions will improve for businesses and businesses will become more competitive. In addition, another important issue that will make significant contributions to the increase in the competitiveness of national companies is the increase in investments in the development of infrastructure. Investments to be made in the field of transportation and communication in particular make significant contributions to the increase in the competitiveness of national companies. Because there is a need for effective communication channels for the marketing of products and important transportation networks and vehicles for the delivery of marketed products to consumers. Therefore, it is extremely important to develop the country's infrastructure in order to increase national competitiveness. In addition to these, export incentives to be given in this process to increase exports and foreign trade and initiatives aimed at integration with international markets make significant contributions to the increase in the international competitiveness of companies. Because in order to increase exports, both the production volume needs to be increased and the product quality needs to be increased. This causes an increase in competition between companies operating in national markets, which is a desired development from an economic perspective. Finally, ensuring macroeconomic stability in the country also contributes positively to the increase in investments at the national level and causes an increase in competition between companies.

2. IMPORTANCE OF INITIATIVES TO INCREASE NATIONAL COMPETITIVENESS

It is possible to say that the concept of national competitiveness is based on more than one theoretical basis and that both foreign trade, economics and business economics theories are used while shaping the concept of national competitiveness. Therefore, the concept of national competitiveness is included in the scope of the study area of these research disciplines. Each of these research disciplines defines the concept of national competitiveness from different perspectives. Within this scope, the World Economic Forum considers national competitiveness as a combination of factors, policies and institutions that determine the productivity level of a country; while the Management Development Institute defines national competitiveness as the ability of the state to provide an environment that will enable businesses in the country to create more value and enable its people to achieve high welfare (Gökmenoğlu et al. 2012: 5). Competitiveness at the national level depends on the high productivity performance of economic activities and the ability to direct production to productive activities that will lead to high real incomes. Competitiveness is associated with increasing living standards, developing employment opportunities and a country's ability to continue to fulfill its international obligations (Erdem and Köseoğlu, 2014: 53). There is a complementary relationship between national competitiveness, industrial competitiveness and institutional competitiveness. Business competitiveness and industrial competitiveness form the basis of national competitiveness. Business competitiveness determines the competitiveness of the industry; industrial competitiveness affects national competitiveness and national competitiveness affects industrial competitiveness and business competitiveness. Improving business competitiveness and industrial competitiveness ultimately depends on increasing national competitiveness (Yurttañıkılmaz et al. 2020: 657). One of the most important elements that determine national competitiveness in any industry is the formation, organization and management of firms in the domestic competitive environment. Because how firms are formed, organized and managed is shaped according to the international competitive environment. The strategies, objectives and organizational structures of firms in an industry differ for each country. Therefore, there is no standard methodology that will suit every sector or firm. A management model needs to be developed that will enable each firm to adapt to the competitive environment it is in. Local conditions affect the structure and strategies of companies. A low competition environment in the sector makes that sector more attractive. On the other hand, an intense competition environment will cause companies to develop their competitive capabilities and seek to create innovation. Therefore, the competitive situation, sector characteristics and strategies to be implemented are of great importance when carrying out business activities (Aslan and Manavgat: 2021: 72).

A stable national competitive power can provide the necessary environment for wealth creation, but it may not be sufficient to create prosperity on its own. Prosperity will be provided by businesses with micro competitive advantage that can take a share from national and world markets by evaluating national competitive power. Macro and micro competitive power maintain a cooperative relationship that involves mutual dependency rather than conflict. Therefore, the data revealed by competitiveness indices contain clues for businesses as well as national and international organizations (Işık, 2023: 1215). In order to determine whether resources are used effectively and efficiently in a country, it is necessary to compare the competitiveness of the country in question in its trade relations with other countries. Competitiveness comparisons can be made in terms of all sectors of the economy (national competitiveness) or on a specific industry or sector basis. National competitiveness comparisons are included in the reports published by the World Economic Forum (WEF) and the World Competitiveness Center (IMD) (Gültekin, 2017: 131). Increasing the national competitiveness, which aims to strengthen a

country's economic performance and position in the international arena, is extremely important. The initiatives that stand out for this purpose can be listed as technological development and R&D expenditures, educational investments in human capital, development of physical infrastructure, ensuring macroeconomic stability and ensuring ease of doing business.

2.1. Technological Development and R&D Expenditures

One of the most important elements that have a direct impact on national competitiveness is technological development and R&D activities. Today, increasing globalization and technological innovation movements have eliminated the boundaries between countries and increased the competition between companies, industries and countries more than ever. In an environment where competition is so intense, traditional production systems have given way to new generation production systems based on knowledge, R&D and innovation. This change in production systems has also caused competition to change dimensions. It is no longer enough to produce any product or service at a lower cost to provide competitive advantage, and issues such as efficiency, quality, speed and flexibility have also gained great importance. Therefore, today, the understanding of competitiveness is experienced in the field of information and technology. Accordingly, in order for companies and countries to achieve sustainable competitive advantage, they need to keep up with technological change by allocating more resources to R&D and innovation (Erdem and Köseoğlu, 2014: 51). For this reason, it is extremely important to increase the share of the private sector in R&D activities by ensuring public and private sector cooperation, to ensure efficient use of resources, to increase knowledge transfer through university-industry cooperation, and to provide physical infrastructure support to companies in these regions by creating certain technology development zones (Yaşar and Dayanan, 2024: 158). In other words, it is of great importance to follow technological developments and to attach importance to R&D activities in order to increase national competitiveness.

2.2. Educational Investments for Human Capital

Today, in knowledge-intensive industries that provide high wage income and have high productivity and are the determinant of national competitive power, basic production factors such as raw material and labor quantities do not provide an advantage. What is important for these industries are factors such as scientific infrastructures and the provision of qualified labor that will meet their needs and provide competitive advantage. If nations are successful in creating production factors in industries, they gain competitive power (Aslan and Manavgat: 2021: 71). The education system is one of the important institutional structures that affect competitive power in the world economy. The fact that rapid technological change in the world economy is the most important factor determining competitive power has increased the importance of institutions by providing the training of qualified people who will train creative people who produce technology and ensure the rapid application of new technologies to production. Qualified human resources are one of the necessary prerequisites for national competitive power and technological superiority. Competitive power based on unqualified and cheap labor only exists for a short time. The only way to maintain, protect and develop competitive power for a long time is to strengthen competition and increase qualification levels (Bal et al. 2023: 24). For this, a qualified workforce that can use advanced technologies effectively is needed.

2.3. Development of Physical Infrastructure

One of the basic elements affecting the increase in the level of sectoral productivity is the state of the infrastructure. Public or non-public expenditures on infrastructure can increase the productivity of a sector. In this context, Porter clearly stated that infrastructure conditions are a

highly effective variable for a sector to compete in national or international markets. As a result of the provision of this infrastructure, a strong competitive potential will emerge and the sector will be more open to development (Firat and Eraslan, 2020: 942-943). In this context, it is possible to say that the development of the physical infrastructure for the production process is extremely important in terms of achieving national competitive power. In order to achieve national competitive power and to rise to higher levels in terms of economic development, it is vital to first determine the institutional and physical infrastructure deficiencies in every field related to the logistics sector and to implement the necessary regulations on the subject. At this point, the contributions of infrastructure investments, especially in the field of transportation, to the reduction of transportation costs will positively affect the entire economy (Emirkadı and Balcı, 2023: 993). Information and communication technologies also provide very important support for businesses to gain competitive power. This support causes structural changes for businesses. Today, businesses can gain competitive advantage if they adapt to these important changes in information and communication technologies. Businesses that gain competitive power can continue their lives efficiently and effectively in intensely competitive environments (Aslan and Manavgat, 2021: 90). For this reason, the development of infrastructure for communication technologies is extremely important in terms of achieving national competitive power. In line with this information, it is of great importance for governments that aim to increase national competitive power to implement a number of incentive policies to develop the physical infrastructure for both transportation and communication activities.

2.4. Ensuring Macroeconomic Stability and Institutional Structure

Ensuring macroeconomic stability is also extremely important for companies in terms of gaining national competitive power. Businesses feel secure and turn to investment in an economic structure where economic balance is achieved, inflation is at relatively low levels and public borrowings develop in a balanced way, and they may compete with each other in this process. The qualitative development in the economy and the competitive power gained accordingly require the existence of a suitable investment and competition environment at the most basic level. The investment and competition environment can be associated with many factors, especially institutional structure and macroeconomic stability. It is accepted that taxes, which have an effect on the level and structure of costs, profitability and demand, have an important place among these factors (Karagöz, 2023: 441). In addition, regulations and practices aimed at increasing the savings rate and capital efficiency also contribute to the increase in competitive power at the company (industry) and national level (Gündüz and Parlak, 2022: 119). In addition, the protection of the production process and production activities by law will contribute to the emergence of a more secure legal structure. In addition, the development of a corporate management approach will allow the emergence of a good management structure and the management of businesses by more qualified and competent managers. These developments will make businesses more competitive. Therefore, the creation of an absolutely reliable investment environment is of great importance in order to achieve and increase national competitiveness.

2.5. Ensuring Ease of Doing Business

One of the important elements that make national companies competitive is the convenience and support to be provided to companies during the production process. In the context of production and state incentives, national production and industrial policies are used to ensure the economic independence and security of a country. These policies may include incentives to protect national interests and industries, to employ domestic labor, and to increase

the competitiveness of domestic companies (Efe, 2024: 138). Within this scope, tax incentives, low-interest loans, provision of space for production activities, and provision of the energy needed in the production process to manufacturers at low costs to be provided by the state allow companies to achieve ease of doing business and directly contribute to the increase in the national competitiveness of companies. In addition, the implementation of legal regulations that increase the ease of doing business for companies with the regulatory reforms implemented and the reduction and, if possible, complete elimination of bureaucratic obstacles also allow companies to increase their competitiveness by providing ease of doing business.

3. IMPORTANCE OF NATIONAL COMPETITIVENESS IN TERMS OF ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT

It is possible to say that increases in national competitiveness directly affect economic development. Increases in national competitiveness are extremely important especially in terms of sustainable economic growth. Because increases in national competitiveness help a country achieve permanent and sustainable economic growth by ensuring that production factors are used efficiently and innovatively. In addition, countries with high competitiveness at the national level can have a say in international markets and contribute to the development of the country's economy. In addition, thanks to national competition, production is carried out with the latest technology and this leads to an increase in product quality. In other words, high value-added production can be realized. This is possible with an educated workforce and an efficient production structure. However, thanks to increases in national competitiveness, exports can increase with increases in both product quality and production volume, and naturally, foreign exchange revenues increase. In this process, it is seen that new or differentiated products in production outputs are of great importance for increasing national competitiveness and exports, and this situation gives a special meaning to R&D activities that form the basis of the innovation process (Karagöz and Şener, 2023: 314). In addition, increases in national competitiveness lead to the emergence of new sectors, national investments increase, and accordingly, employment opportunities in the country increase. In other words, companies with high competitiveness create large employment opportunities in the regions where they are located and ensure the participation of the workforce in the production process, resulting in increased productivity and efficiency, thus contributing to economic growth and development (Sain and Bozkurt, 2023: 480). In addition, it is possible to say that increases in employment opportunities will contribute to the increase in the income level of individuals and the welfare level of society. Finally, it is possible to say that countries with high national competitiveness will attract the attention of international investors in terms of investment environment. Because international investors prefer stable and efficient economies to invest. Increases in foreign investments lead to increases in technology transfer to the country, knowledge transfer and production capacity.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

National competitiveness is extremely important for the development of national economies. National competition, which can be expressed in its most general form as the competitive environment that firms or sectors within the country face during the production process, has very important benefits for the national economy. Increases in the level of national competition primarily cause the technologies used in the production process to develop. Because firms competing with each other can realize both high-quality and high-volume production thanks to and with the help of new technologies. In addition, the intensive use of technology in the production process also allows the production of products with standard characteristics. In this context, national competition allows the intensive use of new technologies, which allows

both increases in production volume, improvements in product quality and the realization of standard production. It is also possible to say that increases in the level of national competition will positively affect the level of employment by causing the formation of new sectors. In addition, improvements in product quality due to increases in the level of national competition contribute to the increase in export revenues by causing increases in exports. Income obtained from exports directly enables economic growth and the development of the country. In order to achieve these economic results, emphasis should be given to R&D activities for the development of technology in the country, importance should be given to investments to be made for the development of human capital and an educated workforce that can use new technologies should be created, emphasis should be given to the development of physical infrastructure for the successful and effective realization of production activities and within this scope, transportation and communication infrastructures should be developed, a macroeconomic environment should be created where investors can feel secure by providing improvements in economic indicators and financial incentives should be provided by the state in the form of tax reductions, low-interest loans, space provision and reduction of production costs in order to create a healthy production environment and ensure ease of doing business, and bureaucratic obstacles that may be encountered after the production process should be reduced. In this way, it will be possible to increase national competitiveness and increase the welfare level of the society by positively affecting economic development with increases in national competitiveness.

REFERENCES

1. Aslan, M. E. ve Manavgat, G. (2021). Yeni Ekonomide Teknolojik Gelişmelerin Uluslararası Rekabet Gücüne Etkisi: Türkiye’de E-Ticaret SWOT Analizi. *Toros Üniversitesi İİSBF Sosyal Bilimler Dergisi*, 8(14), 67-92.
2. Bal, H. Ç., Kutluay Tutar, F. ve Sever, Y. (2023). Competitive Capacity of The Provinces In Tr71 Level 2 Region, Located in the Middle Point of Turkey, in Terms of Tourism Sector, *Turkish Journal of Management & Economics Research*, 4(1), 21-39.
3. Efe, A. (2024). Teknolojik Çözümlerin Yerli ve Milli Söylemi Üzerinden Değerlendirilmesi. *Ekonomik ve Sosyal Araştırmalar Dergisi*, 5(2), 135-163.
4. Emirkadı, Ö., & Balcı, H. (2023). Türkiye’de Karayolu ve Demiryolu Yolcu ve Yük Taşımacılığı ile Ekonomik Büyüme İlişkisi: Panel Veri Analizi. *Kafkas Üniversitesi İktisadi ve İdari Bilimler Fakültesi Dergisi*, 14(28), 977-998.
5. Eraslan, İ. H. ve Fırat, S. (2021). Bölgesel Kalkınma Çalışmalarında Geleneksel ve Tamamlayıcı Tıp Sektörünün (GETAT) Rolü: Düzce İli GETAT Sektörünün Uluslararası Rekabetçilik Analizi Çalışması. *Dokuz Eylül Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü Dergisi*, 23(2), 925-956.
6. Erdem, E. ve Köseoğlu, A. (2014). Teknolojik Değişim ve Rekabet Gücü İlişkisi: Türkiye Üzerine Bir Uygulama. *Bilgi Ekonomisi ve Yönetimi Dergisi*, 9(1), 51-68.
7. Gökmenoğlu, S. M., Akal, M., & Altunışık, R. (2012). Ulusal Rekabet Gücünü Belirleyen Faktörler Üzerine Değerlendirmeler. *Rekabet Dergisi*(52), 3-43.
8. Gültekin, S. (2017). Türk Fındığının Uluslararası Rekabet Gücü: M.Porter’in Diamond Elmas Modeline Göre Bir Değerlendirme. *Kesit Akademi Dergisi*(11), 129-149.
9. Gündüz, M., & Parlak, N. (2022). Ekonomik Kalkınma, Rekabet ve İnovasyon İlişkisinin Panel Veri Analizi ile İncelenmesi: G20 Ülkeleri Örneği. *Uluslararası Sosyal Bilimler Akademik Araştırmalar Dergisi*, 6(2), 117-133.

10. Işık, F. (2023). OECD Ülkelerinin Rekabet Performansının Entropi Tabanlı GİA Yöntemiyle Değerlendirilmesi. Uluslararası Yönetim Akademisi Dergisi, 6(4), 1214-1230.
11. Karagöz, H. ve Sener, S. (2023). Sanayi sektörü önemini yitirdi mi? İhracat ve rekabet gücü ekseninde bir inceleme. İstanbul İktisat Dergisi, 73(1), 307-331.
12. Karagöz, H. (2023). Vergi Gelirleri ve Vergi Yapısının Ekonomik Büyümenin Sürdürülebilirliğine Etkisi: Refah, Verimlilik ve Rekabet Gücü Perspektifinde Bir İnceleme. İstanbul Ticaret Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Dergisi, 22(46), 438-457.
13. Sain, K. ve Bozkurt, K. (2023). OECD Ülkeleri İçin Küresel Rekabet Gücü ve Beşerî Sermaye Arasındaki İlişkinin Analiz Edilmesi. Yönetim ve Ekonomi Dergisi, 30(3), 475-491.
14. Yaşar, S. ve Dayanan, D. (2024). Yüksek Teknolojili Ürün İhracatında Ar-Ge Harcamalarının Rolü: OECD Ülkeleri İçin Panel Nedensellik Analizi. EKOIST Journal of Econometrics and Statistics(41), 151-160.
15. Yurttaçıkılmaz, Z. Ç., Reziwangılı, Y. ve Emsen, Ö. S. (2020). Çin ile ABD Arasında Ticari Gerginlik: Rekabet Gücü Açısından Bir Bakış. Atatürk Üniversitesi İktisadi Ve İdari Bilimler Dergisi, 34(2), 649-667.